

Neutronic Depletion Analysis of Gadolinium Self-Shielding and Spatial Discretization Effects in the PRATIC PWR-SMR Core

Andrea J. Maroni^{1,*}, Gregory K. Delipei¹, Pascal Rouxelin¹, Maria Avramova¹, Kostadin Ivanov¹

¹Department of Nuclear Engineering, North Carolina State University, 2500 Stinson Drive, Raleigh, NC 27695, USA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803418

ABSTRACT

The strong interest in Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) requires advances in modeling and simulation and associated uncertainty analysis to address current challenges in the design, licensing, and deployment of these reactors. The PRATIC benchmark is designed to investigate the behavior of PWR-type, soluble-boron-free (SBF) SMRs. The removal of boron induces higher gadolinium-bearing fuel to compensate for excess reactivity, so accurately predicting depletion behavior in PRATIC requires particular attention. This work develops a full 3-D Serpent model of the PRATIC start-up core and performs various pin resolution depletion calculations to quantify, in particular, the influence of ^{155}Gd and ^{157}Gd self-shielding. The performance of different spatial discretization schemes is assessed. The analysis shows that at least 10 axial nodes and 8 radial nodes are necessary to accurately predict the burnup behavior of Gd-bearing rods. Reference results are provided for a case with 16 radial and 10 axial nodes. The k_{eff} flattens between 2 and 7 MWd/kgU, and criticality is maintained up to 12 MWd/kgU. The pin power distribution shows a maximum value of 2.89 at beginning-of-cycle and decreases to 2.0 at the end of the cycle. The study will serve as a baseline for future modeling of PRATIC or equivalent SMR cores. The resulting discretization guidelines support future PRATIC equilibrium-cycle studies and envisioned multiphysics calculations.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, Serpent, PRATIC, SMR, Discretization

1. INTRODUCTION

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) are emerging as a promising technology in the global effort to achieve decarbonization and improve energy security, and affordability, with more than 100 designs being investigated worldwide [1]. Their compact size, modular construction, and inherent safety features position them as viable candidates for flexible, reliable, and low-carbon electricity generation. Among the SMR concepts currently under development, several are based on light water reactor (LWR) technology due to its proven operational reliability and extensive industrial experience. To address challenges related to the design, safety, license, and deployment of such European Light Water SMRs (LW-SMRs), the EASI-SMR project was launched in 2024 [2]. As part of this project, the PRATIC reactor concept [3] was developed by the French Atomic Energy and Alternative Energy Commission (CEA), to establish a reference benchmark for the systematic evaluation of SMR modeling and simulation (M&S) and assessment of associated uncertainties. PRATIC was also, recently, incorporated into an international OECD/Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) benchmark initiative related to LW-SMRs M&S [4].

The PRATIC initiative seeks to provide a controlled environment to characterize core neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and multiphysics coupling under steady-state and transient conditions. The PRATIC core design is based on pressurized water reactor (PWR) features and with technological concepts of modern SMRs. Its configuration is consistent with compact PW-SMR designs such as the Chinese ACP100, adopting a comparable number of fuel assemblies and low thermal power ($350 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$) to achieve lower

*amaroni@ncsu.edu

linear heat rates and enhanced safety margins (≈ 115 W/cm and ≈ 300 W/cm as the average and maximum for PRATIC, compared to 180 W/cm and 430 W/cm as the average and maximum linear heat rate for current commercial PWRs). Each assembly follows a typical 17×17 UOX pin lattice with enrichment up to 5 wt% in ^{235}U . The core is surrounded by a heavy steel reflector to minimize neutron leakage and extend the fuel cycle length. The PRATIC core adopts a soluble-boron-free (SBF) PWR design. This approach removes dissolved neutron absorber from the primary coolant and eliminates the need for boron concentration control during normal operation. The benefits of SBF cores are (a) reduced corrosion of structural materials, (b) the elimination of large volumes of borated liquid radwaste, (c) removal of both boron-dilution accident scenarios, (d) no degradation of the moderator temperature coefficient, and (e) reduced complexity of chemical and volume control systems. Consequently, the elimination of soluble boron simplifies the operation and maintenance of the plant and removes boron-related initiating events. However, eliminating soluble boron introduces a significant amount of excess reactivity that must be compensated for throughout the cycle by other means.

In SBF PWR cores, burnable absorbers — most commonly gadolinium-bearing ($\text{UO}_2\text{-Gd}_2\text{O}_3$) are combined with full rods and partial control rod insertion during operation. Burnable absorbers are also required to limit power peaking and maintain an acceptable power distribution during flexible operation with frequent power fluctuations. A detailed neutronic analysis of the core is required to quantify the impact of gadolinium depletion on the evolution of the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) and on the corresponding changes in power distribution throughout the fuel cycle. The large absorption cross sections of ^{155}Gd and ^{157}Gd produce strong spatial self-shielding within Gd_2O_3 -bearing fuel rods. Consequently, the ^{155}Gd and ^{157}Gd depletion patterns differ significantly from those of standard UO_2 pins. Although this behavior is known, the gadolinium-related depletion effects may be further amplified in such a compact core configuration. Accurately capturing this behavior requires a spatially resolved representation of the gadolinium-poisoned rods.

The present work develops a three-dimensional (3D) full-core Serpent model of the PRATIC start-up core configuration and performs a depletion analysis to evaluate the influence of gadolinium self-shielding on core behavior. Different radial-axial fuel discretizations are investigated to guide the spatial modeling requirements needed to represent gadolinium-bearing fuel in soluble-boron-free PW-SMR cores reliably.

2. PRATIC CORE CONFIGURATION

The start-up core described in this work corresponds to Version 1.4 of the PRATIC benchmark. It is intended to validate the neutronic modeling approach and define the reference state for subsequent equilibrium-core studies. General design parameters of the PRATIC start-up core are summarized in Table I.

Table I. PRATIC nominal operating conditions.

Parameter	Units	Value
Thermal Power	MW_{th}	350
Moderator pressure	bar	155
Inlet coolant temperature	C	285
Outlet coolant temperature	C	314.32
Average fuel temperature	C	470.55
Mass flow rate	kg/s	2185.39

The core contains 57 fuel assemblies arranged in a compact square layout with an assembly pitch of 21.5313 cm, surrounded by a heavy radial reflector composed of SS304 (95 vol%) and water (5 vol%). The active fuel height is 200.56 cm, bounded by two 20 cm reflectors made of approximately 45 vol%

stainless steel and 55 vol% water. The pin pitch is 1.2618 cm. Fuel pins consist of UO_2 or $\text{UO}_2\text{-Gd}_2\text{O}_3$ pellets with a radius of 0.4107 cm, surrounded by Zircaloy cladding and water moderator. Seven fuel-assembly types are employed in the PRATIC start-up configuration, differing in uranium enrichment and gadolinium loading. The core loading pattern is shown in Figure 1. The central assembly (C1) contains fuel enriched to 2.5 wt.% in ^{235}U and includes eight Gd_2O_3 -bearing rods. The internal assemblies (I1, IE1, IE2) span enrichments from 1.5 wt.% to 3.5 wt.% with varying gadolinium loadings, while the external assemblies (E1, EE1, EE2) use enrichments up to 5 wt.% and incorporate between 8 and 28 poisoned rods.

Figure 1. PRATIC start-up core loading pattern (Version 1.4).

Reactivity control in PRATIC is performed through an array of absorber rod clusters organized into four banks. Three of these are grey banks, composed of mixed silver-indium-cadmium and stainless-steel rods, allowing for fine regulation of reactivity during operation. The fourth is a black bank composed entirely of silver-indium-cadmium rods. Additional shutdown banks, identical to the black clusters are present for SCRAM events. In this work, all-rods-out (ARO) conditions were used, and consequently, these control rods were not included in the model.

3. COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

This section summarizes the specific implementation approaches adopted for modeling the PRATIC start-up core.

3.1. Neutronic Code and General Setup

Depletion simulations were performed using the Serpent code. Serpent is a continuous-energy Monte Carlo reactor physics code developed by VTT that supports steady-state, depletion, and transient calculations [5]. Version 2.2.3 was used together with the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data libraries.

The core was modeled at 100% nominal power operating conditions with ARO, using a full three-dimensional pin-by-pin representation. Quarter-core rotational symmetry was applied, taking advantage of the symmetry of the PRATIC configuration. Vacuum boundary conditions were imposed on the outer model boundary. A total of 5×10^4 particles per cycle were used with 1600 active cycles and 200 inactive cycles for transport calculations. The resulting statistical uncertainty (1σ) on (k_{eff}) was on the order of 15 pcm.

3.2. Geometry, and Discretization

The core was modeled explicitly using detailed pin-level geometry within each fuel assembly. Fuel, moderator, cladding, guide tubes, and instrumentation tubes were modeled as concentric cylindrical regions with dimensions and materials consistent with the benchmark specification. Depletion is performed for each fuel rod individually, using increasing levels of axial and radial discretizations (with the pellet subdivided into concentric rings of equal thickness). The radial discretizations allow the code to resolve the strong radial gradients in Gd-155 and Gd-157 depletion and their impact on the local absorption and reaction rates during burnup. Standard fuel pins without gadolinium were kept homogeneous in radius, with only axial discretization. The reference case has 16 radial and 10 axial nodes (16R/10A). A total of 6 different cases are considered:

1. 2 radial and 10 axial nodes (2R/10A);
2. 4 radial and 10 axial nodes (4R/10A);
3. 8 radial and 10 axial nodes (8R/10A);
4. 16 radial and 2 axial nodes (16R/2A);
5. 16 radial and 4 axial nodes (16R/4A);
6. 16 radial and 6 axial nodes (16R/6A).

Burnup steps were selected to provide good resolution at the beginning of the cycle, allowing an accurate evaluation of the depletion of burnable poisons and the appearance of xenon. A total of 20 depletion steps was used for an end-of-cycle (EOC) burnup of 16 MWd/kgU.

3.3. Materials and Temperatures

The material densities followed the benchmark definition. Fuel densities were treated as smeared values accounting for dish and chamfer volumes, and porosity due to sintering. Rod-averaged values are used for composition and density of the UO_2 and $\text{UO}_2\text{-Gd}_2\text{O}_3$ rods in the fuel assemblies. The reflector was modeled as homogenized stainless steel 304 and water mixtures, with 95 %vol SS304 / 5 %vol water for the radial reflector and 45.1 %vol SS304 / 54.9 %vol water for the axial reflector

Constant material temperatures corresponding to 100% nominal power were applied. Fuel temperature was set to 743.7 K, corresponding to the 3D-averaged fuel temperature. The moderator temperature was set to the average coolant temperature between inlet and outlet (573.15 K). Cladding, gap helium, and structural materials were assigned the same temperature as the moderator.

3.4. Outputs

The primary responses extracted from the simulations were the k_{eff} and the three-dimensional pin-level power distribution. The maximum local peaking F_q and the maximum radial peaking $F_{\Delta H}$ (axially integrated) are computed at each burnup step. These quantities were used to assess the effect of spatial refinement on gadolinium depletion behavior.

4. RESULTS

The following results present the behaviour of the PRATIC start-up core under burnup for all the discretization cases defined in Section 3. The main goal is quantifying the effects of spatial refinement on integral (k_{eff}) and local (F_q , $F_{\Delta H}$) quantities to assess the level of discretization required to obtain accurate results while maintaining an acceptable computational cost compatible with full-core depletion simulations. Furthermore, the results for the reference case are presented and discussed as a preliminary contribution to the PRATIC benchmark.

The evolution of the k_{eff} and the two peaking factors F_q and $F_{\Delta H}$ is presented in Figure 2. Figure 2a, Figure 2c, and Figure 2e show the results for the reference case (16R/10A), while Figure 2b, Figure 2d,

and Figure 2f show the discrepancies from the reference for all remaining cases. First, the reference results are analyzed.

As can be seen in Figure 2a, at beginning-of-cycle (BOC), the core exhibits a strong negative reactivity contribution due to xenon, which offsets the initial excess reactivity of the fuel. As Gd-155 and Gd-157 begin to deplete, the net absorption decreases and k_{eff} rises accordingly, reaching a local maximum once most of the strong absorbers have burned out. Following this initial phase, k_{eff} remains nearly constant over a short interval, reflecting the balance between the continuing removal of residual gadolinium absorbers and the buildup of plutonium fissile isotopes. Beyond this region, the reactivity decreases approximately linearly with burnup, consistent with the behavior of UO_2 fuel once burnable absorbers are depleted.

Figure 2c shows the evolution of the F_q pin power-peaking factor for the reference case. At BOC, F_q has its maximum of 2.89 due to the strong flux depressions around Gd-bearing pins, which force adjacent unpoisoned rods to carry more power. As Gd-155/157 deplete during early irradiation, this localized absorption weakens and the flux becomes more uniform, producing the initial drop in F_q . Beyond this phase, F_q continues to decrease while the core approaches its reactivity peak. After this point, fissile depletion and plutonium buildup introduce growing spatial heterogeneity, causing k_{eff} to decline and F_q to level off and then rise modestly toward the end of the cycle. In Figure 2e, a similar behavior is observed for the $F_{\Delta H}$ pin power-peaking factor with a maximum of 1.79 at BOC.

Second, the impact of the different discretization levels is analyzed. It is important to mention that only an impact larger than the statistical uncertainty is meaningful. This corresponds to discrepancies larger than 60 pcm for the k_{eff} , above 5 % for the F_q , and higher than 2 % for the $F_{\Delta H}$. From Figure 2b, very large discrepancies are observed for the cases with 2 and 4 axial nodes. Even the case with 6 axial nodes leads up to 250 pcm discrepancies towards the EOC. This is also the case for the peaking factors in Figure 2d and Figure 2f. For this reason, at least 10 axial nodes are recommended for the pin depletion of PRATIC. Regarding the radial discretization, from Figure 2b, Figure 2d, and Figure 2f at least 8 radial nodes are recommended.

To better understand the Gd-155 and Gd-157 burn rates, in Figure 3 their radial relative concentrations, normalized to the initial concentration, are shown for different burnup steps. For these results, the middle height slice from one representative 8 wt.% Gd_2O_3 -bearing rod was used. As expected, initially the radial profile of both Gd-155 and Gd-157 is flat. Progressively with burnup the outer regions deplete faster than inner ones. The Gd is completely depleted by 13 MWd/kgU (core burnup). Of course, the exact burn rate of each Gd_2O_3 rod depends on the local power and thus can vary significantly.

Finally, the last set of results presents the radial and axial power distribution at BOC, middle-of-cycle (MOC), and EOC in Figure 4.

Figure 4a shows the radial power distribution at BOC. The highest power occurs in the central C1 assembly. Assemblies with significant Gd loading (E1, E2, E3) exhibit depressed thermal flux and correspondingly lower pin power. Local power maxima appear at the interfaces between unpoisoned and Gd-bearing regions due to the strong localized absorption of Gd-155/157. The resulting pattern follows the fourfold symmetry imposed by the quarter-core modeling approach and reflects the heterogeneous enrichment and gadolinium distribution of the start-up loading pattern. The axial power distribution at BOC (Figure 4b) shows the expected cosinus shape. At MOC (8 MWd/kgU), the radial power distribution (Figure 4c) changes significantly due the depletion of the Gd-155 and Gd-157. The peak power is now located in the assemblies with higher enrichment that are not on the core periphery (E3,E2,I1). The axial power distribution (Figure 4d) starts to flatten due to the higher fuel depletion in the middle. At EOC (Figure 4e and Figure 4f), the previous effects are even more pronounced due to the increased fuel and poison depletion.

 (a) k_{eff} for the reference case.

 (b) Δk_{eff} discrepancies for all cases.

 (c) F_q for the reference case.

 (d) ΔF_q discrepancies for all cases.

 (e) $F_{\Delta H}$ for the reference case.

 (f) $\Delta F_{\Delta H}$ discrepancies for all cases.

 Figure 2. Reference k_{eff} , F_q , and $F_{\Delta H}$ evolution and discrepancies between cases.

Figure 3. Radial Gd-155 and Gd-157 relative concentration evolution over burnup

5. CONCLUSIONS

The work performed a full-core Monte Carlo depletion analysis of the PRATIC start-up configuration, focusing on the depletion of Gd-bearing fuel pins and the influence of spatial discretization. The reference model, using 16 radial and 10 axial subdivisions, accurately captures the evolution of k_{eff} and the pin power-peaking factors. The convergence study shows that at least 8 radial rings and 10 axial layers are required to accurately represent the self-shielding and depletion of Gd-bearing rods. Coarser discretizations introduce significant discrepancies: above 250 pcm in k_{eff} and more than 5% in the pin power-peaking factors toward end of cycle. The validated reference model captures the expected behavior of the start-up core, including the reactivity flattening between 2 and 7 MWd/kgU and the monotonic reduction of the peaking factors as gadolinium burns out. The resulting discretization guidelines ensure reliable depletion predictions at a computational cost compatible with routine full-core Monte Carlo simulations. These results provide support for future work on multi-physics calculations and equilibrium-core analyses.

REFERENCES

- [1] NEA. *The NEA Small Modular Reactor Dashboard: Third Edition*. OECD Publishing, Paris (2025).
- [2] Tulkki, Ville, Sanchez-Espinoza, Victor Hugo, and Sobacki, Nicolas. “Main goals and research outcomes of the EU Projects ELSMOR, McSAFER, and EASI-SMR: regulatory, experimental and analytical safety-related investigations.” *EPJ Nuclear Sci Technol*, **volume 11**, p. 33 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2025023>.
- [3] Vuiart, Romain, Eustache, Aimeric, Eveillard, Sarah, and Prulhière, Géraud. “PRATIC: A soluble-boron-free, pressurized water cooled, SMR core benchmark.” *EPJ Nuclear Sci Technol*, **volume 10**, p. 25 (2024). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2024026>.
- [4] NEA. “https://www.oecd-neo.org/jcms/pl_106827/light-water-cooled-small-modular-reactor-benchmark-for-uncertainty-quantification-and-propagation-in-multiphysics-simulations-lw-smr.” Accessed: 23 November 2025.
- [5] J. Leppänen, V. Valtavirta, A. Rintala, and R. Tuominen. “Status of Serpent Monte Carlo code in 2024.” *EPJ - Nuclear Sciences & Technologies*, **volume 11** (2025).

(a) BOC radial distribution.

(b) BOC axial distribution.

(c) MOC radial distribution.

(d) MOC axial distribution.

(e) EOC radial distribution.

(f) EOC axial distribution.

Figure 4. Reference radial and axial power distribution at BOC, MOC, and EOC